

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Stern**FIRST NAME:** Arthur**PROGRAM CODE:** DIRD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** GulmaThe author applied US*The student must use Turabian/Chicago*The author did notThe author did

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

5 Key Concepts for Writing a Sound Academic Essay

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-12)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
4. Understanding Chicago Style (EUCLID 2021, 43-57)
5. Sample Corrections (EUCLID 2021, 65-72)

WRITING A SOUND ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

When I decided to get another doctorate, I performed a pretty exhaustive search of schools that offered a doctorate in Interfaith Relations. I knew I wanted to study in this area, and I was excited to find the program at Euclid University. I was somewhat disappointed to learn that my very first class would be a writing class. I have written three theses and a dissertation. I have always been able to write adequate research papers and have had some writing classes. I was not very excited to have to take another writing class. I also have always hired an editor to review all my major papers to be sure they all met the requirements of either APA or Chicago style of writing.

Getting acclimated to the LMS system and online courses at EUCLID has presented some challenges however, I believe I have now navigated that well, and I feel much more comfortable with the requirements of the program. I will say that all this took a little time, and I had to get used to not having any sort of in-class presence.

I read the ACA-401D course pack that was refreshed by Professor Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma, and I definitely learned some valuable insights from the material. The course pack also refreshed my memory in certain areas and reinforced my current knowledge in others. I also watched the assigned videos for period one, and they were

helpful as well. I realized through this class that it would be prudent for me to brush up on some of the skills I have not used for a while. I realize that for me to produce a worthwhile essay, I must have a firm grasp on the basics of writing a well-written research paper. I further grasped that paying attention to small details is critical when writing a paper.

In this response paper, I will discuss five main concepts that I received the greatest amount of learning from in the ACA-401D course pack assigned for period one. The main areas I will discuss are essay writing, plagiarism, style, understanding Chicago Style, and sample corrections within a response paper.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The course pack for period one begins with looking at the types of essays people write. There are many different types of essays a person can write. For academic purposes, it is most common to write scholarly non-fictional papers that are part of academic work. The course pack states, “Academic essays seek to provide an answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence” (EUCLID 2021, 7).

I found it very useful to review some of the basic steps that are involved in writing an academic essay or research paper. I have done these steps in the past since I have written many academic papers while obtaining the multitude of degrees I have. However, this review reinforced some of my practices and reminded me of others. It is critical to get an early start; I have employed this theory in all my advanced degrees. Appropriate research time and time to contemplate the topic and material, think about it, and write it are critical to the success of assembling a well-written paper (EUCLID 2021, 7).

Employing the proper definition and analysis of the question the writer is attempting to answer is another important part of the process. It is also important to understand and write all that the writer has learned about a particular topic however this is secondary to analyzing and presenting the answers to the key question the writer is asking (EUCLID 2021, 7).

It is also important to have a plan. Most people do not plan to fail they just fail to plan. Many times, a concise outline is a critical part of this process of planning. Writer should document their thoughts and ideas related to their topic. These thoughts and ideas will be incorporated into the initial outline to help give some overall direction and this process will be integral in guiding the writer’s research (EUCLID 2021, 7). The information in the course pack reiterated to me how important it is to have a well-thought-out plan and an organized outline. This entire process will help greatly in understanding what information is relevant to your paper and what information may not be helpful.

I liked the pyramid that was in the course pack that outlined the steps for writing a research essay. Researching the topic thoroughly is where it all begins. I was reminded of the fact that I needed to look at what I already knew about the topic and decide what else I needed to know and fill in the gaps in my knowledge. This requires me to sift through

information and determine what is useful and what may not be useful in making my argument or presenting my topic (EUCLID 2021, 8).

The next step is organizing my ideas. As my ideas become more apparent and concrete in my mind and on paper then I can develop a plan for writing which for me also involves writing an outline to keep me on track and moving in the right direction. This will help me maintain sight of the goal. If I am well organized in my approach then it will be easier to select the relevant and appropriate information to include in my essay. The course pack reinforces this approach “Look through your notes and choose examples to provide evidence to support your answer” (EUCLID 2021, 8).

The rules of thumb outlined in the course pack on pages 12-14 helped summarize and direct my thinking for a well-thought-out and well-organized research paper. Stating the main thesis of my paper in the first paragraph reminded me that I need to pay attention to this in all my research papers. Next, I was reminded of how important it is to stay focused. It is easy to allow ourselves to get off-center and lose focus and motivation. I liked what the course pack said in this section “But do not try to provide a comprehensive overview of the theory. Instead, guide your presentation by the particular problems that animate your paper” (EUCLID 2021,13).

Writing clearly and in a concise manner is something I always need to remember and focus on. The course pack is correct when it says this is much easier said than done. I am reminded in the material to write short sentences and not to allow run-on sentences to bore my reader. It is also critical to have shorter paragraphs and not to let paragraphs run on for an entire page. The course pack gives some excellent guidelines for evaluating these two points. It tells me that if a sentence goes on for more than five lines shorten it. If a paragraph is more than twenty lines break it up. It also resonated with me to be sure that I write in a simple understandable language (EUCLID 2021,13).

“When you finish writing, read your paper out loud. Writing that does not sound right will not read right” (EUCLID 2021,13).

3) PLAGIARISM

The chapter on plagiarism was a great reminder for me. It also gave a complete synopsis of what plagiarism is and why it is important not to commit this act when writing a research essay. It summarized many topics in the sphere of plagiarism that I want to be aware of all the time when writing a research paper. This needs to be at the top of my list when writing. The course pack clearly states “When writing papers, one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism” (EUCLID 2021, 34).

The definition of plagiarism as given in the course pack is “plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2021, 34). Plagiarism is taking someone else’s ideas or words and then copying and pasting them into your paper and not giving credit to the original author and not citing the proper source in the proper manner. Plagiarism is also having someone

else write a paper for you and then put your name on it. Then submitting that paper as if it was your work originally would also be considered plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34).

In the well-rounded argument surrounding plagiarism, I was reminded of why it is important to cite the source and give appropriate credit. The course pack lists the three main reasons why it is important not to plagiarize.

Plagiarism is wrong and unethical,

It is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit, and

It is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences (EUCLID 2021, 34).

I further liked the concise manner presented on how to avoid plagiarism. The course pack states, "In order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to correctly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using" (EUCLID 2021, 34).

Reviewing all the ways to cite sources of information in a research paper was also a great reminder for me. I needed to brush up on this area. There are two key methods of citing, In-text citations and lists of works cited (EUCLID 2021, 35). The course pack then explains all the different ways of citing. This was a very helpful reminder and will be an excellent reference guide for me throughout the entire doctoral program.

4) STYLE GUIDE

The next point of interest to me in the course pack for this period was "The Style Guide." The course pack states, "A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent" (EUCLID 2021, 41). I learned that style guides relate to types of writing. It is important to have published guidelines so that there is consistency and that the final essay does not display the writer's personal style. The final product should more accurately display the style of the publication, company, or other source associated with the essay (EUCLID 2021, 41).

I learned a deeper understanding of a style guide for writing essays that I had never thought about in the past. This information will be useful as I write papers for this program. The course pack reiterates, "A style guide provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing that will allow you to ensure consistency in your written output" (EUCLID 2021, 41).

Euclid recommends using the Chicago Rules (Turabian) style for the basic rules for writing research papers. While punctuation and grammar are important aspects of a paper and have well-established and clear guidelines, the style itself is much more than just the correct usage of these items (EUCLID 2021, 41). Some of the important aspects of style I learned from the material are:

Preferred sentence lengths,
Manuscript layout,
Depth of treatment of a subject,
Readership considerations,
Accepted terminologies,
Structure, and
The use of lists (EUCLID 2021, 41-42).

I did not list them all, and the course pack tells me the list could be longer however, I think this clearly makes the point that style does vary and there are many components. These are all items that I need to consider when writing my essays.

Freelance writers should find a style guide to be of particular importance. “Freelance writers should continually develop style guides for each customer or publication type that they work with” (EUCLID 2021 42). To increase the satisfaction of their customers’ freelancers will want to develop a style that is congruent with their customers’ desires. This will help to increase customers’ satisfaction and keep them interested in reading the writer’s published works (EUCLID 2021, 42).

5) UNDERSTANDING CHICAGO STYLE

I have been fortunate enough to write in The Chicago Style of writing for research papers in some of my past degrees. My last Thesis for my master’s Degree in Rabbinic Studies was written in Chicago Style. This chapter was a good refresher for me since I wrote that paper over three years ago. The chapter begins by referring to two books most widely associated with The Chicago style for writing papers. “Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian’s Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press)” (EUCLID 2021, 44). I have read a significant portion of Turabian’s book and found it very informative and useful in writing essays.

The chapter also pointed out the dictionaries that are most useful and accepted for matters of spelling. The course pack cites Webster’s Third New International Dictionary and Meriam -Webster’s Collegiate Dictionary. I am more familiar with the latter. In instances where the two references may differ in their spelling or definition, the Collegiate should be followed. It represents the most recent publication and is considered the more credible of the two (EUCLID 2021, 44).

The chapter speaks to proper abbreviations, capitalizations, compound word usage, italics, quotation marks, numbers, and quotations. All of these were good reviews for me

to consider as I write essays for my doctoral program and the course pack will be a good reference guide for these areas.

Some areas of learning for me are that abbreviations that I may commonly use in other writings I do are not appropriate for a research paper or essay for this class (EUCLID 2021, 44). There are also three main areas for capitalization, full caps, heading caps, and sentence caps. Full caps are used to capitalize every letter of every word. Heading caps are used exclusively when capitalizing only the first letter of each word. Sentence caps are used to capitalize the first word of a title or heading (EUCLID 2021, 45).

I had not thought about using compound words for a very long time. The course pack relates “compound words are two or more words that work together in a specified order. This order cannot be reversed or rearranged without destroying the compound words meaning. A dictionary is the best guide for spelling and usage” (EUCLID 2021, 46).

The other area of interest to me was the area of quotations and how they are to be cited. “Quotations must be placed in quotation marks or indented as a block quote” (EUCLID 2021, 48). It is also proper format to be sure and includes a citation or a note to the reader for each quotation. The course pack also informed me that it is important for quotations to flow with my writing and if necessary, I can edit them to do so (EUCLID 2021, 48).

The last learning, I received from this chapter was Chicago page formats. The chapter outlines the various formats that are acceptable under Chicago Style. It speaks to required margins, type of fonts, indents, acceptable paper type, justification, spacing, and page numbers (EUCLID 2021,50). These were a good refresher for me and helped me remember some details I might have forgotten.

6) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS

The last area I will cover in this response paper is the chapter on sample corrections. This chapter was especially useful. It gave me a look at what type of corrections might occur in my papers and how they would be displayed. Seeing this in an actual paper is helpful as I have to write many of these papers for my doctoral program. Some of the corrections in formatting are ones I might commonly have in some of my papers.

I also was able to see how the errors in the paper in the course pack could detract the reader’s interest. This might discourage the reader from absorbing the material or continuing to read the paper. Under the Plagiarism heading, there were many errors in formatting that distracted me from writing.

I think the greatest learning in this chapter was how visible it became to me that all these details I may have taken for granted matter more than I realized. If I want to write an effective research paper or essay then I will need to pay great attention to the details. This is critical if I want my reader to desire to read my papers. I never really thought much about this however this chapter has raised my awareness.

7) CONCLUSION

The material compiled in the course pack and writing this response paper helped give me a greatly needed refresher course in some of the details I had forgotten that are integral to the process of writing a well-researched and well-written essay. It provided a good starting point for the papers I will need to write in my doctoral program. It took a little time to get used to some of how this course will operate however I believe this is a good start.

This period caused me to realize that the details are important, and I must pay adequate attention to them as I continue to write essays for my classes. If my intention is to write effective scholarly papers, then I will need to master the skills laid out in the course pack for this program. I have been a lifelong learner, and this coursework to begin this program has been a good indicator for me that I need to be open-minded and continue to learn.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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